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Lead Beneficiary:

Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC): Sandro Fiore, Donatello Elia, Cosimo Palazzo, Alessandro D'Anca

Other contributing authors:

DDN: Jean-Thomas Acquaviva

Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ): Niklas Röber, Dela Spickermann, Florian Ziemer

Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie (MPI-M): Oliver Heidmann

Seagate: Hua Huang

The University of Reading (UREAD): Julian Kunkel, Luciana Pedro

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1. Introduction

This report provides an architectural view of all the data management components (“data theme”) set up in the ESiWACE2 project. It provides insights into the design of the ESDM interface for supporting data-intensive *post-processing*, *analytics* and *visualization* (PAV) and case studies from the weather and climate change domain. The document addresses the milestone MS5.1 of the ESiWACE2 project. More in detail, starting from background work and the description of the main use cases targeted by the ESDM, a set of technical requirements for the ESDM unified API has been identified, with a strong focus on the new PAV layer for in-flight analytics and visualization. The general ESDM architecture is introduced, highlighting the main components for I/O and processing. The proposed architecture tries to address the identified requirements and provides the guidelines to steer the development stage through the definition of the main architectural components, the relationship among these and some preliminary technical details.

The document is mainly intended for internal use, although it is publicly released. The main target of this document is the ESiWACE2 consortium team from the different Work Packages, in particular, WP1 for the end-to-end simulation workflows and, of course, WP4 and WP5 for the data management systems.

The rest of the document is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a brief summary of the data theme view. Section 3 describes some relevant background work about the ESDM and software involved in the selected WP5 post-processing, analytics and visualization applications. Section 4 is about the main use cases addressed by the ESDM infrastructure and it is aimed at highlighting the features required by the ESDM at PAV and I/O level. Section 5 identifies the main functional and non-functional requirements that the ESDM should provide at PAV level, while Section 6 provides a more schematic description of the use cases with respect to the overall ESDM interface. Section 7 depicts the ESDM architectural components, their internals and the interaction among them, as well as the analytics kernel. Section 8 provides a preliminary overview of the ESDM deployment with respect to the defined use cases. Finally, Section 9 drives the main document conclusions.

2. Data Theme View

Figure 1 provides the Pert chart related to all the data systems activities provided for in the project. In particular, it shows the task dependencies among WP1, WP4 and WP5, which respectively relate to the (i) climate and weather numerical high-resolution simulations on pre-exascale supercomputers, (ii) the data systems at scale with respect to ensemble tools and storage middleware and finally, (iii) data post-processing, analytics and visualisation support for a selected set of applications.

In particular, the project plans a preliminary version (across WP4 and WP5) of the ESDM architectural document at M12 (described in this document) and a final one at M15. It is worth noting that such design takes also into account “data” requirements coming from the end-to-end numerical simulations defined in WP1.

Figure 1. Data Theme View

3. Background

This section provides some relevant background regarding the ESDM components developed in the previous phase of ESiWACE, three selected applications on data post-processing, analytics & visualization and two storage technologies from industry partners, which will provide the new requirements for the ESDM extensions planned for in the project.

3.1. ESDM

The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) aims to exploit heterogeneous storage landscapes by concurrently utilizing the available storage and allowing meaningful subsets of data to be placed on different storage systems as required. The ESDM targets concurrency from a single parallel application providing dynamic data granularity. The main ideas behind this software-centric co-design effort to address the I/O challenges are:

1. High-level semantics, i.e., awareness of application data structures and scientific metadata, and
2. Flexible mapping of data to multiple storage backends.

Figure 2. ESDM software architecture

The ESDM architecture is sketched in Figure 2. While ESDM provides its own interface, it deeply integrates into NetCDF and the Python module for NetCDF, allowing a seamless integration into existing workflows.

Internally, a NetCDF “file” is mapped to a container consisting of datasets and metadata. ESDM uses the site configuration to make layout decisions by splitting a dataset into fragments. A fragment is stored on exactly one storage backend, but as a dataset typically consists of many fragments, data of a dataset is scattered among backends locations.

Further information is provided in [Deliverable 4.2](#) of the first phase of ESIWACE. [Kunkel, 2017].

3.2. CDO

As the CDO documentation states, “*The Climate Data Operator (CDO) software is a collection of many operators for standard processing of climate and forecast model data*” [Schulzweida, 2019]. The operators include simple statistical and arithmetic functions, data selection, subsampling tools, and spatial interpolation. CDO was developed to have the same set of processing functions for GRIB [GRIB, 2003] and NetCDF [Rew, 1990] datasets in one package.

The Climate Data Interface (CDI) is used for the fast and machinefile format independent access to GRIB and NetCDF datasets and it is independent from a specific data format. The local MPI-MET data formats SERVICE, EXTRA and IEG are also supported.

There are some limitations for GRIB and NetCDF datasets:

- GRIB datasets have to be consistent, similar to NetCDF. That means all time steps need to have the same variables, and, within a time step, each variable may occur only once. Multiple fields in single GRIB2 messages are not supported.
- NetCDF datasets are only supported for the classic data model and arrays up to four dimensions. These dimensions should only be used by the horizontal and vertical grid and by the time. The NetCDF attributes should follow the GDT, COARDS or CF Conventions.

The main CDO features are:

- More than 700 operators available
- Modular design and easily extendable with new operators
- Very simple UNIX command-line interface
- A dataset can be processed by several operators, without storing the interim results in files, by chaining operators on the command-line.
- Most operators handle datasets with missing values
- Fast processing of large datasets
- Support of many different grid types
- Tested on many UNIX/Linux systems, Cygwin, and MacOS-X

Each operator is executed in a separate thread where each finished record is passed to the operator as soon as possible. Internally, CDO manages its data propagation through a set of streams. These streams are pipe and file streams. File streams are the input-output components which enable reading/writing data from or to files. Pipe streams are used to provide finished results to the next operator for processing. The file streams read and write their data through the use of CDI while the pipe streams use CDO internal logic. For future extensions, more streams (e.g., ESDM-Stream) could be implemented. A generic stream interface class is included in the CDO repository.

3.3. High-Performance Data Analytics

The Ophidia project provides a High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) framework joining HPC paradigms with scientific data analytics approaches [Fiore, 2013][Fiore, 2019]. Although the framework is primarily exploited in the climate domain, it provides a domain-agnostic architectural design that makes it suitable for any scientific domain dealing with multidimensional data formats [Fiore, 2017]. Ophidia provides in-memory, parallel, server-side data analysis and I/O, an internal storage model and a hierarchical data organization to manage large amounts of multidimensional scientific data (see Figure 3) [Elia, 2016]. It supports the execution of (parallel) interactive and batch operations and complex workflows of operators.

Figure 3. Ophidia data analytics framework architecture

The Ophidia HPDA framework architecture is composed of multiple layers. The Ophidia Server exposes multiple server interfaces to submit analytics workflows or single jobs. Currently, it provides (i) a web service WS-I interface compliant with WS-I Basic Profile v1.2 and based on SOAP over HTTPS, (ii) a GSI-enabled interface with support for Virtual Organizations (VOMS) and (iii) a web service compliant with the OGC-WPS standard. It also takes care of the management, scheduling, submission and monitoring of analytics jobs over HPC schedulers (e.g., SLURM, LSF). It implements the functionalities to parse and validate the workflows of jobs provided in accordance with the Ophidia JSON schema [Palazzo, 2015].

In its second layer, Ophidia provides a framework for the execution of parallel tasks, named operators, that run on compute nodes over multidimensional distributed data. The framework includes an extensible, API-based environment for the development of new parallel operators able to conceal, at the same time, the complexity of the hierarchical and distributed data organisation. Currently, Ophidia contains more than 50 data cube operators that allow, for example, data import, export, subsetting, reduction and metadata management.

The third layer is devoted to the I/O and analytics operations on the underlying data. I/O and Analytics servers implement this layer and run the Ophidia primitives (a wide set of array-level operations) on the data stored according to the Ophidia storage model [Fiore, 2013]. The current version includes about 100 primitives that support, among others, mathematical and statistical functions, interpolation, regression, mining, selection and several other features. Ophidia supports two types of I/O and analytics servers: (i) MySQL RDBMS, and (ii) the Ophidia native in-memory service.

The *OphidiaDB* is the Ophidia system catalogue that manages a MySQL RDBMS. It stores the information about the system configuration, its status, the registered users, the list of I/O and analytics servers, the job status and history, and the physical mapping of the datacube fragments into the storage system.

The storage system is the hardware resource that manages data store, namely the physical resources hosting the datacube fragments according to a hierarchical and distributed storage structure. Resources can be local, distributed or parallel systems.

3.4. Data Visualization

The main software employed at DKRZ for the 3D visualization and analysis of simulation output is ParaView [Ayachit, 2015], an open-source software developed by Kitware and the ParaView community. ParaView is able to read a number of different file formats, including regular gridded NetCDF data, as well as ICON netCDF/Grib compressed data, along with other netCDF variations, such as MPAS. ParaView is an extremely powerful and flexible visualization framework, and the aforementioned NetCDF readers allow using all filters, visualization and analysis techniques available within ParaView. A detailed examination of the correlations between two or more variables can easily be done using scatterplot matrices and a parallel coordinates view, whereas the Topology Toolkit, a set of additional ParaView Plugins, can be employed for topological data analysis.

As for the visualization of very large data sets, ParaView can be used in a client-server setting, in which several ParaView data/render servers process data in parallel and connect to a single visualization client for a faster I/O and processing/rendering. In case of even larger simulations, ParaView provides the Catalyst extension that, together with a model-dependent Catalyst Adaptor, allows performing in-situ visualization and processing of the simulation output.

Over the recent years, ParaView has become an essential tool in our workflow, not only for the visualization of various simulation outputs and measured data (e.g. satellite output), but also for model debugging and interactive 3D data analysis. The internally developed ICON reader is based on CDI and uses it as an interface to access and read data dimensions and data variables. As such, it can also read GRIB compressed ICON data sets, either as a single file or as a data file series. A number of additional filters make it our primary tool for the visualization and analysis of high resolution simulation data.

3.5. Storage Technologies

Seagate and DDN are two major storage solutions providers, both enjoy a worldwide presence and a strong portfolio of products in HPC and the Enterprise market. Another similarity between the two companies is the importance of their R&D effort. While competing on some market segments, Seagate and DDN often cooperate on specific research activities.

For this project, Seagate is using Mero, its object storage base platform, and its base API Clovis, to efficiently store weather and climate data, as a data backend in ESDM. Advanced features, like In-Storage Computing of Core Mero will be helpful to offload some computation from client nodes to storage nodes.

Within the scope of the project, DDN leverages the Infinity Memory Engine® (IME®) to accelerate applications performance by eliminating prominent I/O bottlenecks. IME incorporates modern storage technologies such as non-volatile memory (NVM) devices and efficiently exploits many-core processor architectures to provide a scale-out, software-defined, flash storage platform that streamlines the data path for application I/O. Applications can directly benefit from using IME without the need of any modification. Part of this project's tasks is the integration of IME's custom API with NetCDF. A similar effort is already ongoing with the SIONlib I/O library.

4. Target use cases and applications

This section describes a complete set of use cases/applications from a user perspective, relevant to the ESDM PAV extensions and, in general, the data management activities planned in ESIWACE2. In particular, it deals with: data post-processing, analytics and visualization applications as well as industry Proof of Concept and simulation workflows.

4.1. CDO

To be able to handle the ever-growing size of simulation data, we will investigate the potential of classic performance optimization, improve the parallelization of CDO, and possibly outsource the computationally heavy routines to specialized hardware such as GPUs.

Typical CDO operations are arithmetic operations combining multiple variables, spatiotemporal subsetting, spatiotemporal statistics computation, data remapping, and the computation of differences and correlations between different data sets.

In the context of the ESIWACE2 project, we analyse the prospects of providing selected GPU accelerated operators and, if possible, we will provide prototypes of such operators. Furthermore, we will introduce the **ESDM PAV** API into the CDO workflow.

4.2. High-Performance Data Analytics

Currently, data can be stored as database tables or in-memory objects in the Ophidia HPDA framework. The integration with ESIWACE ESDM will allow Ophidia to **transparently interact with multiple types of storage backends** for I/O operations (e.g. POSIX, object store, semantic storage, cloud-based storage).

In terms of analytical operations, the integration with the ESDM PAV layer will allow the Ophidia framework to easily exploit a **wider and more portable set of analytical kernels**. Additionally, thanks to this integration, Ophidia can also exploit the data parallelization for in-flight data analytics provided by ESDM PAV.

Once the integration is performed, the climate-based and also workflow-based analytics use cases developed through the Ophidia HPDA framework will serve as proper validators of the ESDM PAV.

4.3. Data Visualization

The current visualization/data analysis workflow performed at DKRZ, and in many other centers, follows the classic post visualization setup. In this workflow, the necessary data for visualization/analysis is written to disk during the simulation run, it is eventually further processed and finally read in again for data visualization/analysis. Due to the high storage costs and I/O bandwidth/performance limitations, this classic post-visualization is a sensible approach only for “lower” resolutions. To handle the large simulation output anticipated in ESIWACE2, two visualization strategies are considered and followed up on as part of this work package. As described in the project proposal, either an **in-situ data visualization/processing** and/or a **progressive rendering** approach using wavelet decomposed data appear to be the only solutions. Prototypic implementations of both options exist for the model ICON, which need to be integrated into one component/API that can easily be applied and transferred to the other ESIWACE2 models [Röber, 2019][Jubair, 2016].

4.3.1. In-Situ Visualization/Processing

Due to great familiarity with ParaView, we have looked at utilizing ParaView's in-situ extension Catalyst for initial in-situ visualization experiments. We have implemented a Catalyst Adaptor, as described in the Catalyst manual [Bauer, 2015], that binds the FORTRAN code of the simulation model ICON to the C++ code of ParaView/Catalyst. Figure 4 shows an overview of the current approach. A data multiplexing, i.e. the simultaneous forwarding of data to different processing/visualization sinks, is thereby explicitly desired, thus data from the same simulation can be used to create snapshots, perform in-situ feature tracking and for in-situ LoD decomposition (see Section 4.3.2).

With the existing implementation, we have conducted several in-situ visualization experiments, including one at R2B10 resolution (2.5km global atmospheric simulation run), employing 540 nodes of the Mistral supercomputer at DKRZ. In this setting, we were able to run a script that was generated by ParaView using sample data, thresholded two 3D variables (cloud water and cloud ice) in-situ with parallel I/O, as well as generating standard visualizations (images).

We are confident that this approach is directly applicable to higher resolution model runs of ICON, such as R2B11 and beyond, that is the long-term goal of ESIWACE.

Figure 4: In-Situ Data Visualization and Processing.

The next tasks are a consolidated implementation that not only fits ICON, but it can be applied to all other ESIWACE2 models as well (see Section 4.3.3). This also includes the development of suitable and easily deployable workflows for climate scientists working with these simulations.

Requirements & Implementation Details: The three main steps for a Catalyst-based in-situ visualization are, see also [Bauer, 2015. Section 3]:

- Initialize (Catalyst needs to be initialized, usually done after `MPI_Init()`. This includes the transfer of the grid layout and coordinates as mesh.)
- CoProcess (The processing function that is called during the simulation run to transmit data variables and to actually perform the in-situ processing/visualization.)
- Finalize (After completion of the simulation, Catalyst needs to properly shut down, before `MPI_Finalize()` is called.)

ParaView also provides a number of Adaptor examples, ours is based on the Fortran/C++ example¹. An in-situ processing can either be done loosely or tightly coupled. According to a recent study [Kress, 2019] that was presented at ISC 2019, the best approach for large simulations with a high number of MPI processes/nodes, is a tightly coupled setup with a balanced number of simulation MPI tasks and Catalyst MPI tasks.

4.3.2. Progressive Rendering

In-situ visualization has a number of advantages, yet also a few drawbacks. One of the downsides is the required a priori knowledge to create the Python script that Catalyst needs for processing the simulation output. Especially after increasing the spatial and/or temporal resolution and the addition of new physical/chemical/biological processes, the correct setting of thresholds and color tables is difficult. In these cases, it would be desirable to be able to interactively access the entire data set in full resolution.

¹ <https://gitlab.kitware.com/paraview/paraview/tree/master/Examples/Catalyst>

To accomplish this, a progressive rendering with a Level-of-Detail (LoD) decomposed data can be used. Progressive rendering is simply the visualization of a lower resolution version of data, which also allows loading details to reconstruct a higher resolution representation on demand. Examples are online mapping services and the JPEG image compression algorithm.

A visualization application that allows progressive rendering using LoD data is the open source software VaPOR [Shaomeng, 2019], which is developed by NCAR in Boulder, Colorado. VaPOR supports regular and irregular grids, but not yet a progressive rendering on irregular grids.

The LoD decomposition of the simulation data can either be done globally as part of the I/O servers with a parallelization over the z-axis, or directly on node and in-situ by complying with a few boundary conditions. While the first approach is the most common and easiest to implement, it still requires the transmission of all data over the network to the dedicated I/O servers for processing. The latter is more efficient and less communication intensive, yet it requires a domain decomposition that allows an easy and simple downsampling.

4.3.3. Online Processing API

The current implementation of the online processing is entirely based on the API that is prescribed by VTK and the design of a ParaView/Catalyst Adaptor [Bauer, 2015]. To be more flexible, we anticipate a more generalized API that should, nevertheless, also satisfy the requirements for in-situ visualization using ParaView/Catalyst. This API should not only be suitable for one simulation model, but for all models that are followed up on within ESIWACE2. Furthermore, it would be great to be able to employ CDO as additional processing library to transform the existing simulation output from NetCDF into for example a Cinema² database, or an LoD decomposed data set for progressive rendering. Cinema is an image based visualization strategy that shows previews of the data, as well as providing excerpts of important subsets of the simulation output via a web interface.

As said, the API needs to be as general as possible, though still supporting an in-situ visualization using ParaView/Catalyst. As for large simulations, a tightly coupled in-situ visualization is much more effective; we have been striving to implement the online processing API in a similar manner, i.e. having a balanced (same) number of MPI simulation and processing/visualization tasks on one node. During model spin up, “local” grid information has to be transferred using zero copy from the FORTRAN model code to the C++ processing code, along with a description (in Python code) of the data processing/visualization that needs to be done.

4.4. Industry Proof of Concepts

The ESDM PAV will be responsible for the execution of the analytical kernels related to the data transformations needed by the project use cases and classified according to the following categorization: statistical, selection, arithmetic, interpolation and transformation. However, some simple data reduction could be performed via specific kernels implemented at the storage-level. We refer to them as active-storage kernels. This activity will need a co-design phase with the vendors

² <https://cinemascience.github.io/>

involved in the ESIWACE2 project to understand the extent by which some data reduction will be possible at the level of storage back-end.

Considering the higher complexity and potentially limited support available at the storage level, the targeted data reduction would only be simple statistical kernels (e.g., max, min, avg, sum); the possibility to perform data sub-setting based on conditions will be investigated too.

- In-Storage Computing (a.k.a Function Shipping) of Mero/Clovis from Seagate is feature offloading computation from Mero/Clovis clients to storage servers. Data reduction is a typical function which can be offloaded to storage servers to avoid data transportation. This can reduce network traffic and operation delay. Simple statistical kernels (e.g., max, min, avg, sum) can be directly implemented as a function in Mero/Clovis and executed on storage servers.
- DDN effort for in-storage computing is based on research activities related to the NGI interface. At the moment we have a running prototype leveraging the read patch in the storage server. A read request is annotated in order not to trigger a read on the storage server but to trigger a function applied to the read data, and only the results of the operation are transferred back to the compute cluster. While this is at the research stage, we have already a minimalistic simulator written in C. One obvious limitation to address is to prevent computation errors on the storage servers (what happens in case of divide by zero). This problem can be addressed by only allowing predefined compute kernels to be executed on the storage server through a validated library for instance. However, the key technical challenge is intrinsic to parallel file systems: as files are striped on multiple servers, the operation has to be applied only to the locally available file fragment. From a mathematical standpoint, it requires commutativity of the operators. As a first step to tackle this, we envision focusing on the function supported by MPI reduction operators. Since striping is done without semantics (storage stores arrays of Byte), the API has to provide some semantics to allow the servers to perform the computation with a byte level addressing scheme.

4.5. Simulation Workflows

The use cases in ESIWACE2 are the highest model resolutions that can still be run with a throughput of 1 SYPD, making them applicable to weather and climate prediction. Based on our experience from ESIWACE1, the models and their respective configurations are:

- EC-Earth: 16 km (TL1279) atmosphere coupled with a 1/12 degree (~8 km) ocean.
- ECMWF: 5 km (TCo1999) atmosphere coupled with a 1/4 degree (25 km) ocean.
- ICON-ESM: 5 km atmosphere coupled with a 5 km ocean, aiming at higher resolutions for the ocean.
- The IPSL model: 10 km atmosphere coupled with a 1/12 degree (~8 km) ocean.

In the traditional climate model setups with an experiment covering 250 years (1850-2100), a large number of 2D and 3D variables is stored to disk for analysis and computation of diagnostics at time intervals between hourly snapshots and monthly averages. For the analysis of cloud dynamic processes, data needs to be stored at a much higher frequency in the second-to-minute range. Weather forecasting

also operates with output in the minute range. The standard model output formats are NetCDF and GRIB. Due to the high computational cost of the simulations aimed for in ESiWACE, shorter total durations will be mandatory, and output frequencies in the hourly to daily range will mostly be used. Currently, MPI-M is performing a simulation at 5 km resolution with an output of 250 GB per simulated day (approx. 100 TB / simulated year). These vast amounts of data require improved workflows that utilize data reduction strategies.

5. Requirements Elicitation

Based on the use cases description provided in Section 4, a set of functional and non-functional requirements have been extracted in order to properly characterize the ESDM PAV architecture.

5.1. Terminology

- **Kernel:** The analytics operations to be performed on data. A kernel is defined by its code and typically consists of one or more elementary operations (verbs) that need to be executed on all data (map operations) and data reduction operations such as max/min (reduce operations).
- **Workflow:** A directed acyclic graph of tasks and their dependency such as computation of kernels and I/O activities that generate required data products.
- **Fragment:** A subset of a dataset that is stored on exactly one storage system. ESDM understands the layout and data type of a fragment and the user-provided metadata.
- **Offloading:** The execution of operations on a remote device closer to the data.

5.2. Functional Requirements

Functional requirements refer to features that the ESDM PAV should provide. These include:

- **In-memory runtime environment:** To address processing speed, ESDM PAV runtime system should provide an in-memory environment to handle data structures from/to the ESDM I/O and for the processing through analytical kernels.
- **Data processing kernels:** ESDM PAV should provide a set of core kernels to address the use case execution. These can mainly be classified as statistical, arithmetic, selection, transformation and interpolation functions.
- **Support for active-storage kernels:** ESDM should allow for the development and execution of simpler kernels which can be offloaded to the storage servers to perform the computation before shipping data from the storage to the processing infrastructure. Higher-level analytical kernels and workflows could be built on this lower-level functions, when available, to implement part of the operation and reduce data transferred over the network.
- **Plugin-based Infrastructure:** ESDM PAV should define a plugin-based infrastructure for analytics kernels in order to make the integration, monitoring, and execution of new kernels straightforward. This will also allow an easy extension of the application with new

functionalities; exploiting the same interfaces or easily including/excluding specific types of kernels.

- **Support for parallel kernels:** ESDM PAV interface should also allow for the implementation of parallel-executed kernels.
- **Support for kernels running on heterogeneous hardware:** The runtime should allow the execution of different types of kernels in terms of hardware architecture (e.g., on GPU accelerators).
- **Operation chaining:** ESDM PAV should allow an easy chaining of multiple operations between data reading and writing in order to build more complex workflows based on lower level analytical kernels.
- **Support for streaming operations:** It should allow the performance of analytical operations in-flight over data streams from the storage by exploiting the underlying ESDM I/O layer.
- **Support for multiple storage backends:** ESDM PAV should provide the PAV applications access to data stored on multiple heterogeneous storage back-ends by exploiting the ESDM I/O features. To this end, the ESDM PAV will provide wrappers to I/O functionalities. This relates to the non-functional requirement “Unified and Integrated API”.

5.3. Non-functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements refer to some properties that the system should guarantee. In some cases, non-functional requirements can also be linked to functional requirements. The identified requirements include:

- **Unified and integrated API:** A single interface, integrating functions for data I/O, access and processing, should be provided in order to ease the exploitation (e.g., in terms of building and compiling) of the ESDM stack into the various use cases. In this regard, the unified interface could be built on top of the ESDM I/O interface providing wrappers for I/O functions.
- **Usable and minimal API:** The ESDM PAV interface should be as lightweight as possible in order to provide a minimal, yet complete, set of interfaces.
- **C-based API:** The ESDM PAV should provide at least a C-based API in order to allow a stronger integration of the module with scientific and HPC-based software. The opportunity to develop other higher-level languages, such as Python, will also be taken into account (optionally).
- **Robustness of the runtime:** The ESDM PAV runtime should be able to handle possible execution errors caused by the underlying analytical kernels.
- **Flexible plugin interface:** ESDM-PAV must take into consideration a variety of analytics usage scenarios, and its interface should allow the exploitation of the features in different contexts and execution modes. This requirement is somehow related to the “plugin-based infrastructure” functional requirement.

- **Extensibility:** The set of ESDM PAV analytical features should be easily extended through new analytical kernels. This requirement is also strongly related to the “plugin-based infrastructure” functional requirement.
- **Efficiency:** The ESDM PAV should provide efficient analytical operations in order to support the defined use cases. This requirement is linked to the “support for parallel kernels” functional requirement.
- **Linux platform support:** the module will be built to target HPC Linux-based software environments in terms of OS, compilers and dependencies.

6. Use Case Diagrams

This section provides a more schematic description of the use cases providing a more in-depth view in terms of interactions with the ESDM system and the performed sub-steps.

Figure 5 shows a use case diagram associated with ESDM PAV. With regards to PAV applications, four use cases are considered:

- Running a data analytics workflow
- Executing a post-processing operation
- Sampling data for a visualisation application
- Compressing/decompressing a dataset transparently during any I/O activity or the aforementioned use cases

In particular, the first case is related to the use of the Ophidia framework to execute a workflow. While task scheduling is directly handled by Ophidia, the application exploits ESDM PAV to execute single tasks: retrieving a dataset from storage, applying a number of data transformation operations (by running the corresponding kernels) and, finally, saving outputs to storage. Therefore, Ophidia framework needs to:

- load the input dataset from the storage and apply an initial operation, for instance a decompression as well as a subsetting operation;
- execute a number of basic operations (implemented by different kernels), back-to-back as well as in parallel, according to data dependencies;
- finalize output data (e.g. by a compression) and store final files.

The diagram shows how these operations are mapped to simple tasks for ESDM PAV: applying a kernel (to be implemented by the analytics kernels engine), reading data from storage and writing data to storage (implemented by ESDM I/O). Note that ESDM PAV has to provide the possibility to apply more kernels back-to-back (the output of one is the input of the next one) avoiding storing intermediate data, thus limiting access to I/O devices.

The second use case considers a CDO command to process a NetCDF file. The command could apply one or more transformations and, in general, produce another NetCDF file as output. In the diagram, this process is represented by the task “Process stored data” and consists of three steps:

- loading the input dataset from storage to PAV memory;
- applying a set of kernels back-to-back;
- storing the output dataset from PAV memory into storage.

The third use case represents the sampling of a dataset. Such an operation could be applied to simulation results in order to avoid pushing a huge amount of data to a visualisation application, reducing processing time and, thus, enabling visual report output datasets while the simulation is running. The application requires that ESDM PAV apply an appropriate selection kernel or more complex operations (possibly implemented by more kernels back-to-back) to the input datasets.

The fourth use case is related to a PAV application that uses ESDM PAV to compress/decompress the input dataset and store the result using ESDM I/O features.

Finally, the diagram also shows the interaction between ESDM PAV and kernel developers. Two use cases are considered: the developer plugs in a new kernel, thus enabling the module to perform a new operation, and the developer starts the execution of a kernel for testing. Clearly, whenever a new kernel is plugged in, it has to be available for any PAV application.

Figure 5. Use case diagram

7. Architecture

This section describes the architecture proposed for the ESDM PAV layer and its interaction with the other ESIWAC2 project components, as well as some preliminary details about the identified internals.

7.1. Architecture Overview

Figure 6. ESDM architecture overview with respect to other project components

The ESDM PAV layer builds on top of the ESDM I/O component to provide data processing features for different applications. In particular, within the scope of the ESIWACE2 project, three types of applications are mainly going to be targeted: post-processing of data, high-performance data analytics and in-situ visualization (described in more detail in Section 4). These applications will also serve as demonstrators of the ESDM PAV implementation. The integration of PAV and I/O features into a single API will allow the application to seamlessly access data stored on different storage devices exploiting the ESDM I/O features as well as to apply one or more kernels on data upon loading or storing datasets.

As shown in Figure 6, the project considers several data flows and, for each of them, specific software modules will be provided to process datasets. At the top of the software architecture there are modules designed to handle workflows: they allow users to define the set of operations to be executed by means of the platform, considering task and data dependencies, decoding workflow descriptions and starting task execution (e.g., Cylc workflow engine). An appropriate task scheduler (e.g., SLURM) assigns the available compute resources during the workflow execution and possibly takes data locality into account in selecting compute nodes to limit network traffic.

Tasks could be ensemble analysis or complex simulations as provided by WP1 (module called “WP1 simulations”). Ensemble services can simply read/write raw data directly from/to the underlying storage system or exploit the service offered by XIOS support (for instance data reduction, in-flight analysis or compression), thus dealing with NetCDF files. In addition, Semantic Storage Tools (SemST) will be provided to search and discovery NetCDF files stored at ESDM level. Finally, tasks are also represented by a number of applications that exploit the ESDM PAV features.

On the one hand, post-processing and data analytics applications can be considered as tasks that read/write persistent datasets directly from/to the storage and require the ESDM PAV features to perform some kinds of data transformation: statistical, subsetting or arithmetic operations as well as data interpolation. On the other hand, in-situ applications are tasks that require the ESDM PAV layer to process transient data to obtain intermediate simulation results and to enable the visualisation of the simulation progress. Clearly, these applications can also require storing some outputs persistently on the underlying storage infrastructure and, in this case, it is expected that they directly exploit the NetCDF interface, as shown in the figure.

As described in more detail in the following, the ESDM PAV layer is able to process data forged by the applications or retrieved from the storage using a set of (parallel) operation-dependent modules (called analytical kernels) whose implementations are well suited for the underlying hardware (e.g. accelerators, GPUs) in order to obtain the maximum performance.

Access to storage is handled by the ESDM I/O modules designed in WP4 and briefly described below. They include the implementation of the NetCDF interface shown in the figure. At the I/O level, ESDM provides a unified interface to a number of storage backends implemented using different technologies (POSIX, object stores, tapes, etc.) and optimizes data allocation by selecting the effective storage system to write data based on the current performance level. In addition, it implements a set of active storage kernels to implement some specific kernels at the hardware level (i.e. statistical/arithmetic or simple sub-setting operations).

7.2. ESDM Main Components

As stated in the previous description, the **Earth System Data Middleware** consists of two main components addressing complementary functionalities: for I/O from/to storage (at WP4 level) and for data processing, analytics and visualization (at the WP5 layer). Next subsections will dive into the details of the two components and their interactions.

7.2.1. ESDM WP4 Architectural View

Figure 7. Updated ESDM architecture

Figure 7, extends our previous architecture for ESDM (see Section 3).

As part of WP5 in ESIWACE2, ESDM is extended to support analytics and visualization workflows. The core idea of the in-transit analytics is to enable analysis and post-processing workflows to exploit available compute capabilities on modern storage architectures. For example, when operations such as reduction or search on a fragment are performed, those operations can be forwarded to the storage backend that, in turn, forwards the request to the storage itself (i.e., of active-storage solutions). This competence minimizes network transfer and maximizes performance. To perform such operations, ESDM must translate from high-level data representations to the low-level byte-array representation understood by storage.

In-situ visualization and analysis of data are related to the post-processing task. It requires a high level understanding of the data semantics and involves some computational tasks that could potentially be offloaded to storage. In this part of the ESIWACE2 project, we intend to develop a single API (ESDM Post-processing, Analytics and Visualization API; PAV in Figure 7) that provides all the functionalities needed to offload data analysis and enables, at the same time, in-situ data analysis. The benefit for users will be that they only have to implement a single API and can utilize the capabilities of all features at execution time without further changes.

The next sections report the changes to ESDM to be made during ESIWACE2.

Data Offloading

In order to enable the processing of data in the I/O path, an additional functionality is required. As part of ESiWACE2, we are interested in the functionality of the read path and ignore the opportunities to write for now.

For the discussion of the functionality, we consider the following example. Assume we have a 2D dataset, dimension (7x6) of a specific data type (single-precision floating-point). The data was sparsely written in two fragments according to Figure 8. Some coordinates of the cells are highlighted. Note that cells (4,3) up to (6,7) have not been written.

Figure 8. ESDM example dataset (dimension 7x6). It is partitioned into two fragments, a cell contains the actual value. The value inside the selected cell is the coordinate.

Read

- A programmer must be able to register the compute kernel for the operations to be performed. Such operations might be complex compositions of individual operations. Instead of reading the data on the client, the result of the computation must be returned by ESDM and by the connected storage.
- We only support the processing on a single data set, hence workflows that span multiple datasets (e.g., give me the maximum of two datasets) will not be developed, yet.

The low-level capability will be implemented as follows. We allow the user to define a streaming function, which is applied to each data element. The computed result of this function is fed into the reduce function. Additionally, multiple results can be fed into a combiner function that must return the same output as the stream function, allowing the local combination of results. It is up to ESDM and the storage backends to parallelize the execution of the stream function and to schedule the execution of combine and reduce functions. The system must ensure the following:

- Each valid element will be processed exactly once with the stream function.
- The reduce function will receive the generated data by the stream function and the information about the missing patches. The reduce function is called only once for each partial result and will

be called on the client node, as typically the final reduction requires data from different storage backends.

The flexibility allows ESDM to further parallelize internally the processing of the fragments in blocks. In our example, the Fragment 1 could be processed by two stream functions and Fragment 2 by one stream function, according to the blocks in Figure 9.

Figure 9. ESDM dataset, a possible parallel processing by the backends for the two fragments. Each block is processed concurrently.

The signature of the function will look like:

```
esdm_status esdm_read_stream(esdm_dataset_t *dataset, esdm_dataspace_t *space,
void *user_ptr, esdm_stream_func_t *stream_func, esdm_combine_func_t *combine,
esdm_reduce_func_t *reduce_func);
```

The signatures of the stream and reduce functions will enable the execution of the stream function on each data element (if not NULL) and the reduce function across all elements (if not NULL). The user may provide additional information via *user_pointer*. Data reduced by map is expected to be smaller or equal in size, but not necessarily.

Example use case: compute minimum, mean and maximum of the dataset.

- The operation can be achieved by computing and returning the variables *cell-count*, *min*, *max* and *sum* for each fragment. Then, the reduce function aggregates the cells together, possibly dealing with the missing patches according to the user expected semantics.

<pre>function stream (cells, user_info, output): count = 0, sum = 0 min = INFINITY max = -INFINITY for cell in cells:</pre>	<pre>function reduce (stream_out, user_info): update min/max/count/sum in user_info->result function combine(stream_out1, stream_out2, user_info):</pre>
---	--

<pre> count++ update min/max/sum according to value output.write(count, min, max, sum) </pre>	<pre> // update the result in stream_out1, e.g.: stream_out1.sum += stream_out2.sum </pre>
---	---

In our example, the two blocks in Fragment 1 could be processed independently with their stream function, then one call to the combiner would produce one result for Fragment 1. Similarly, Fragment 2 would be processed. If both fragments resided on the same storage device (which is unlikely), the combiner could be called again. The final result would be returned to the client, where the reduce function is called for each result and integrates them into the final response.

An issue with remote execution is that the functions must be able to be shipped to the remote system. For flexible handling, we will also offer an `esdm_read_stream_remote` function that extends the signature by a filename indicating a library and the function that shall be executed. The library can then be loaded (potentially cached), and the function will be executed in a similar fashion as indicated above. A difference from the previous execution path is that the user data will need to be transferred to the remote location, but we consider this to be a minor extension.

Low-level Transformation

ESDM will transform the high-level calls into similar calls as provided by the storage APIs from Seagate (Clovis) and DDN (IME). A key difference is that these APIs operate on tuples (size, offset) instead of locations in a dataset. ESDM will translate the dataset coordinates into Byte offsets.

Visualization

Requirements:

- The API must allow the integration of existing Paraview workflows. Thus, the high-level semantics must be provided and stored.
- ESDM node-to-node communication

Write

In the write path, it must be possible to hand the data over to a visualization solution to enable in-situ analysis. This means that no effective I/O will be performed but instead data is handed over to another API. This requires capturing and communicating the following information:

- Grid information, i.e., static grid information known at the beginning about the shape of the Grid. Typically, this information is available in the NetCDF user-provided metadata.
- Already external data must be able to be referenced in the Container. This typically includes grid files necessary to interpret the positions of cells correctly as scientists use indirect indexing.

- Based on the domain decomposition and runtime behavior, further information about the grid must be dynamically integrated, e.g., its shape.
- Optionally, a multiplexing of targets of the data path must be possible allowing the transfer of data to multiple endpoints at the same time, e.g., to the storage and visualization API.

Embedding compute kernels in the write path would be nice to have but it is not the focus of ESiWACE2.

- A programmer must be able to register a set of compute kernels that shall be performed concurrently with writing the data. Similar to the read path, such operations might be complex compositions of individual operations. The result of the computation must be stored by ESDM and by the connected storage as derived data. Example use case: compute minimum, mean, and maximum of the dataset and store it alongside the data. Create a progressive data compression and store it.

7.2.2. ESDM WP5 (PAV) Architectural View

Figure 10 shows a detailed architecture of the ESDM module for *“Post-processing, Analytics and Visualization” (PAV)*. ESDM PAV consists of two main components: the in-memory runtime environment and the analytical kernels engine. A set of core libraries, called analytical kernels, implement specific data processing operations for in-flight data analytics. PAV applications, i.e., post-processing tools like CDO, analytics frameworks as Ophidia and visualization applications like ParaView, as described in Section 4, can exploit the ESDM PAV features by means of the PAV API.

Figure 10. ESDM PAV architecture

In order to address the identified requirements, the ESDM PAV API represents a unified interface for I/O and analytical functions, exploiting the ESDM I/O component for reading and writing data from/to the storage layer. To this end, the API will provide specific wrappers to the ESDM read and write functions, allowing PAV applications to stage in memory datasets into the runtime environment (loading from or storing to storage), besides the interfaces to apply one or more operations (using the required kernels).

The ESDM PAV runtime is responsible for handling ESDM-specific data structures and applying the analytical kernels, while also providing features to dynamically manage data layout organization to better address the required processing. In turn, the analytical kernels engine is responsible for decoding the developer request, selecting and applying the required kernel (also in parallel) and returning the result to the runtime. In order to address the “plugin-based infrastructure” requirements, kernels could be defined as dynamic Linux libraries and dynamically linked, also at runtime, when requested. This adjustment also allows the easy update of an analytical kernel without needing to update the whole PAV application as well as running data analytics operations over different hardware architectures, e.g., traditional CPUs and GPUs.

In terms of functionalities, the analytical kernels should provide the features to perform statistical analysis, data selection and subsetting, arithmetical operations, data transformation and interpolation. Given the generality and flexibility of the plugin-based approach, kernels could provide general-purpose functionalities but also more climate-specific functions. Some examples of kernels are:

- Data selection, including operations to subset according to one or multiple dimensions at once.
- Data aggregation, to compute statistical values (e.g., maximum, minimum, average, variance, quantiles, etc.).
- Arithmetic operations, like multiplication, division, square root, logarithm, rounding, trigonometry, expression evaluation, etc.
- Data interpolation, e.g., for regriding.

Interaction with multiple storage back-ends is handled transparently by the ESDM I/O layer through a set of wrapper functions made available to the developers from the PAV interface.

At the PAV API level, some usage scenarios (at a lower level with respect to the application-based use cases) of the API would be:

1. Gathering data from storage applying an analytical kernel in-flight:
 - a. Loading input data from the storage (using the ESDM I/O layer) in an in-memory stage
 - b. Applying a data analytics kernel in memory (in-flight)
 - c. Providing the processed data to the application
2. Applying an analytical kernel on a dataset stored to produce a new dataset:
 - a. Loading input data from the storage (using the ESDM I/O layer) in an in-memory stage
 - b. Applying a data analytics kernel in memory (in-flight)
 - c. Writing the data back to storage (using the ESDM I/O layer)
3. Applying an analytical kernel on data already in memory:
 - a. Applying a data analytics kernel to a data structure provided by the application
 - b. Providing the processed data back to the application
4. Applying an analytical kernel on data already in memory and storing the data:
 - a. Applying a data analytics kernel to a data structure provided by the application
 - b. Writing the data on the storage (using the ESDM I/O layer)

In each case, data analytical kernels could also be chained one after the other (this applies especially to use case 3). Depending on the specific operation to be executed, ESDM PAV runtime will exploit the ESDM I/O features to load/store data from/to the underlying storage by means of the ESDM API (provided by WP4).

Whereas ESDM PAV runtime provides support for parallelisation (e.g., threading), multiple instances of the same kernel can be assigned with different fragments of the input dataset and perform the

operations in parallel, thus increasing system scalability. To further improve performance, the kernels could be executed over hardware accelerators; in particular, the use of GPU accelerators is required by post-processing applications. The use of dynamic Linux libraries for the kernels, each one built for the specific hardware, makes possible the extension of ESDM PAV to several hardware architectures. Moreover, the ESDM I/O layer will provide support for the execution of low-level kernels by exploiting active-storage functionalities (if available), allowing, in turn, the PAV analytical kernels to build more complex functionalities on these lower level functions.

The development of analytical kernels in the next tasks of the project will be mainly driven by the increasing complexity of the operations to be implemented on the basis of the following steps:

- simple statistical operations as the evaluation of the mean, minimum and maximum value of the input dataset;
- data selection and arithmetic operations;
- complex operations as adaptive sampling, Fast Fourier Transform, wavelet decomposition, compression/decompression, correlation, regression and kernels based on GPU accelerators.

The advancement in implementation, test and integration of the three classes of kernels in the workflows associated with the above use cases will be monitored by the corresponding KPI: statistical (Y2), selection and arithmetic (Y3), interpolation and transformation (Y4).

The support provided by ESDM PAV to applications will be monitored by setting up a prototype integrating software-based analytical kernels (Y3) and by advanced implementations integrating analytical kernels based on accelerators and/or active storage support (Y4). Furthermore, to verify and validate the kernel implementation some benchmarks will be performed.

8. Preliminary use case deployment

This section shows a preliminary use case deployment for one of the selected applications, in particular the High Performance Data Analytics one (Ophidia). Figure 11 provides a preliminary view of the expected integration and deployment of the ESDM components with Ophidia data analytics framework to implement the HPDA use case. This picture represents an extension of the Ophidia architectural diagram shown in Figure 3.

In particular, the Ophidia Analytics & I/O server will be extended to integrate the ESDM PAV API to integrate the ESDM features for (i) transparently accessing multiple storage back-ends for I/O and (ii) executing analytical kernels through the PAV runtime environment.

Figure 11. Deployment of Ophidia and ESDM components for the HPDA use case

Similar diagrams for the other applications described in this report will be provided in the second update of this document by M15 (M4.1).

9. Conclusions

This report provides an initial architectural overview of the Earth System Data Middleware extensions planned for in the ESiWACE2 project, focusing, in particular, on the new layer supporting data post-processing, high performance data analytics and visualization, and its relation with respect to the other ESiWACE2 project components. Besides the specific use cases, it provides a comprehensive set of requirements, an architectural view of the ESDM I/O and ESDM PAV extensions jointly with some examples of analytical kernels and a preliminary deployment diagrams regarding the HPDA application. Requirements and architectural insights also relate to hardware/storage technology aspects, to be addressed in close synergy with the vendor partners of the project (in particular, the support for in-storage analysis). This report will be extended and consolidated with the second architectural document scheduled in M15 (Milestone 4.1).

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